

EXAMINING USER SATISFACTION AND ADOPTION IN SMART BANKING APPLICATIONS : A FOCUS ON BENEFITS

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Abstract. In recent years, the financial markets have seen substantial changes due to the widespread use of technology and the rising acceptance of digital solutions. Smart banking applications (SBAs) are at the forefront of this revolution and offer a wide range of capabilities that set them apart from traditional banking services. The objective of this study is to examine the level of satisfaction and utilisation of a smart banking application in relation to the advantages experienced by users. Data for this specific study was meticulously gathered through a comprehensive questionnaire that was specifically customised for individuals who frequently utilise smart banking services. A total of 150 replies were collected and carefully analysed to draw meaningful conclusions from the study's findings. Based on the findings, benefits have a favourable impact on satisfaction. There was a substantial relationship between satisfaction and both usage and intention to use.

Key words: Smart Banking, Benefit, Satisfaction, Intention to use, Usage

Introduction

Smart banking is an innovative development in the financial services industry that employs advanced technologies to enhance and streamline traditional banking processes [1]. Smart banking utilises a wide range of tools, including conventional means such as smartphones and internet platforms, as well as cutting-edge solutions like AI, big data analytics, and wearable technology. This all-inclusive toolbox empowers users to conveniently access their accounts and efficiently handle their finances while on the move. Additionally, users may receive tailored financial guidance and enjoy enhanced security and convenience of use. Smart banking, whether accessed via mobile apps, internet platforms, or other means, enables individuals to assert authority over their finances and make well-informed choices. This ultimately fosters financial inclusion and cultivates a future where individuals have greater control over their financial well-being. With the growing prevalence of technology and the increasing adoption of digital solutions, the financial markets have seen significant transformations in recent years. Smart banking applications (SBAs) are leading this transformation and provide a plethora of capabilities that distinguish them from conventional banking services. The Small Business Administration (SBAs) has experienced significant expansion, garnering a global user base of millions, as evidenced by a projected market value of \$12.4 billion by 2026 [2, 3].

Telecom providers have had a substantial influence in Sri Lanka, notwithstanding their recent entry into the banking and financial industry. Recent figures indicate that telecommunications companies have successfully expanded the availability of financial services to a significant number of individuals in Sri Lanka [4]. These services have also offered customers more convenient and efficient banking options. Notably, there were over 20 million mobile banking transactions per month in 2023. According to Statistics, With internet access expected to

reach 4.41 million households and mobile internet users exceeding 5.15 million by 2023, Sri Lanka's digital landscape is experiencing rapid growth, creating a fertile ground for the adoption of innovative solutions like smart banking applications [5, 6]. This article aims to explore the benefits that users derive from smart banking applications, specifically the personal value that consumers associate with the properties of the product or service.

Objective

This article aims to examine the elements that influence satisfaction and utilization of smart banking in the Ampara District. Although this paper draws on previous research, its main emphasis is on the advantages experienced by users rather than the specific features of financial services. The investigation focuses on the utilization of several financial services [7,8].

Methodology

Information needed for this particular research was collected with great care using a thorough questionnaire that was specifically tailored to those who are regularly using smart banking services. In order to guarantee the accuracy and credibility of the measurements, the questionnaire utilized measurement tools that were modified from pre-existing literature, reflecting well-established concepts in the domain of smart banking adoption. Participants were requested to articulate their viewpoints and attitudes using a rating system based on Likert scales that spanned from 1 (representing 'strongly disagree') to 5 (representing 'strongly agree'), enabling the collection of subtle and comprehensive insights into their beliefs.

A grand total of 150 replies were gathered and scrutinized in order to derive significant inferences from the study's findings. The participants' demographic distribution exhibited an equitable participation, with 47% of the respondents identifying as female and 53% as male, so assuring a diverse and inclusive sample. It is worth mentioning that a substantial majority of participants, comprising 63%, stated that they possess more than two smart banking applications, indicating a large level of involvement with numerous platforms.

In addition, the frequency at which the respondents used smart banking services provided useful insights into their behavior when it comes to digital banking. Approximately 71% of the participants stated that they use smart banking services on a weekly basis, highlighting the consistent and frequent nature of their involvement with these digital financial applications. The frequent use of smart banking applications indicates an increasing dependence on these apps for the participants' regular financial activities.

Figure 1: relationships between the variables

Hypothesis

H1 : The benefits experienced by users will positively impact their delight with smart banking.

H2 : The satisfaction of utilizing smart banking services will positively impact its usage.

H3 : The satisfaction derived from utilizing smart banking services would positively influence

the propensity to use them.

Table 1 : Model Summary - Regression Analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.930 ^a	.864	.862	.47922
2	.933 ^b	.870	.868	.46926
a. Predictors: (Constant), Intention to use, Usage				
b. Predictors: (Constant), Intention to use, Usage, Satisfaction				

The summary table displays data from two regression models that examine the relationship between variables (Intention to use, Usage, and Satisfaction) and a dependent variable. In Model 1, the predictors exhibit a robust positive correlation ($R = 0.930$), accounting for approximately 86.4% of the variance in the dependent variable. Model 2 improves upon the previous model by including "Satisfaction" as an additional factor.

This results in a higher R Square value of 0.870, indicating a better explanation of approximately 87.0% of the variability. The modified R Square takes into account the number of predictors, and both models provide a low standard error of the estimate, indicating a strong fit. Model 2, which includes the variable "Satisfaction," improves the models' capacity to account for the differences in the dependent variable when compared to Model 1.

Table 2 : ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	214.481	2	107.241	466.970	.000 ^b
	Residual	33.759	147	.230		
	Total	248.240	149			
2	Regression	216.090	3	72.030	327.105	.000 ^c
	Residual	32.150	146	.220		
	Total	248.240	149			

a. Dependent Variable: Benefits

b. Predictors: (Constant), Intention to use, Usage

c. Predictors: (Constant), Intention to use, Usage, Satisfaction

The table 2 provides a comparison of two regression models in their prediction of the "Benefits" variable. The regression analysis in Model 1, which incorporates factors such as Intention to use and Usage, yields a very significant result ($F = 466.970$, $p < 0.001$). This indicates that these predictors make a substantial contribution to explaining the variability in benefits. Model 2 improves upon the previous model by including "Satisfaction" as a predictor, which leads to a significantly better F-statistic (327.105 , $p < 0.001$). Both models demonstrate a substantial capacity to forecast advantages.

Table 3 : Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.626	.080		20.449	.000

	Usage	.067	.008	.474	8.536	.000
	Intentionto use	.071	.008	.496	8.945	.000
2	(Constant)	1.657	.079		21.054	.000
	Usage	.059	.008	.416	7.116	.000
	Intentionto use	.061	.009	.425	7.044	.000
	Satisfaction	.020	.007	.148	2.703	.008
a. Dependent Variable: Benefits						

The sum of squares for residuals quantifies the amount of unexplained variance. All things considered, the ANOVA findings indicate that the predictors as a whole considerably contribute to the variation among the variable that is dependent "Benefits," and Model 2's inclusion of "Satisfaction" further strengthens the model's predictive ability.

The table 3 presents data on the correlation among the variables that are predicted (Usage, Intention to use, and Satisfaction) and the variable that is dependent, "Benefits." In Model 1, the constant term is 1.626, which represents the predicted value of "Benefits" when all of the predictors have a value of zero. Both Usage ($B = 0.067$, $p < 0.001$) and Intention to use ($B = 0.071$, $p < 0.001$) exhibit positive and statistically significant coefficients, indicating that an increase in both variables is linked to a positive alteration in "Benefits."

The constant term in Model 2, which incorporates Satisfaction as an extra predictor, is 1.657. The regression coefficients for Usage ($B = 0.059$, $p < 0.001$) and Intention to use ($B = 0.061$, $p < 0.001$) remain positive and statistically significant, suggesting that they continue to have a positive influence on the "Benefits" variable. Furthermore, the coefficient for Satisfaction is positive and statistically significant ($B = 0.020$, $p = 0.008$), indicating that an increase in Satisfaction is linked to a positive alteration in "Benefits." These coefficients facilitate the comprehension of the magnitude and orientation of the associations between variables and the variable that is dependent in forecasting the perceived advantages by individuals.

Table 4 : Correlations

		Benefits	Satisfaction	Usage	Intentionto use
Benefits	Pearson Correlation	1	.823**	.889**	.893**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	150	150	150	150
Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.823**	1	.796**	.810**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	150	150	150	150
Usage	Pearson Correlation	.889**	.796**	1	.836**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	150	150	150	150
Intentionto use	Pearson Correlation	.893**	.810**	.836**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	150	150	150	150

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table 4 exhibits the associations among several factors in the study. The values denote Pearson correlation coefficients, which quantify the magnitude and direction of linear associations. The factors in this context are "Benefits," "Satisfaction," "Usage," and "Intention to use." The table displays significant positive correlations between the variable "Benefits" and each of the three other variables: "Satisfaction" ($r = 0.823$), "Usage" ($r = 0.889$), and "Intention to use" ($r = 0.893$). These findings indicate that as contentment, usage, and intention to use improve, the perceived benefits also tend to increase. Furthermore, there exist robust positive correlations between the predictors themselves: "Satisfaction" exhibits a strong association with both "Usage" ($r = 0.796$) and "Intention to use" ($r = 0.810$), while "Usage" and "Intention to use" also display a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.836$). In summary, these notable connections demonstrate the interconnectedness of the variables, suggesting that persons, who express higher levels of happiness, engage in more frequent usage, and possess a stronger inclination to use also likely to perceive greater advantages.

Table 5 : Hypothesis summary

Hypot he sis	Statements	Results
H1	The benefits experienced by users will positively impact their delight with smart banking	Accepted
H2	The satisfaction of utilizing smart banking services will positively impact its usage.	Accepted
H3	The satisfaction derived from utilizing smart banking services would positively influence the propensity to use them	Accepted

Conclusion

The notion of Smart banking services has garnered considerable attention as a prospective business model that might supplant conventional online banking services and provide supplementary value through a diverse array of services. Smartphone-based banking plays a vital role for users, banks, and financial institutions. Due to its immunity to temporal and spatial constraints, it has the capacity to improve the quality of life for individuals and lead to enhanced efficiency and cost reduction in the banking industry.

The correlation and regression analysis reveal a statistically significant and positive correlation between the variable "benefits" and the variables "usage" and "intention to use" also This suggests that the satisfaction derived from using smart financial services will have a favourable impact on their utilization. The correlation matrix and regression coefficients of both models suggest a robust and positive relationship between "satisfaction" and "usage." Finally, the gratification derived from utilizing smart banking services will positively influence the propensity to use them. The correlation matrix and regression coefficients demonstrate robust positive correlations between the variables "satisfaction" and "intention to use." The statistical studies provide evidence for each of the three alternatives. There is a substantial correlation between the perceived benefits, satisfaction, usage, and intention to use smart financial services. This suggests that when customers perceive extra benefits, have higher satisfaction, and increase their usage and intention to use, they enjoy heightened levels of satisfaction with smart banking.

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